

Time Management And Personality Traits Among College Students In Private Institutions

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Abstract. Effective time management is a critical self-regulatory skill associated with academic success, productivity, and well-being among college students. This study examined the relationship between time management skills and the Big Five personality traits among college students in the Bacoor area. A quantitative correlational research design was employed, with data collected from 100 purposively selected respondents using standardized instruments, including the Time Management Questionnaire (TMQ) and a Big Five Personality scale. Descriptive statistics and Pearson r correlation were used to analyze the data. Results indicated that students generally demonstrated good time management skills ($M = 3.17$), engaging frequently in planning, organizing, and prioritizing tasks. Personality traits were found to be at moderate levels across all dimensions. However, correlation analysis revealed that extraversion, agreeableness, conscientiousness, and neuroticism had no significant relationship with time management skills. In contrast, openness showed a statistically significant positive relationship ($p = .0034$), indicating that students who are more curious and adaptable tend to exhibit better time management behaviors. The findings suggest that while most personality traits do not strongly predict time management, openness plays a meaningful role in influencing students' ability to manage time effectively. The study highlights the importance of fostering adaptive cognitive and behavioral strategies to enhance time management. Implications support student development initiatives aligned with Sustainable Development Goal 4 (Quality Education).

Keywords: Big Five personality traits; college students; correlational research; openness; time management

Introduction

Time management is a fundamental self-regulatory skill that enables individuals to allocate time efficiently across various tasks to achieve desired goals. It involves planning, prioritizing, organizing, and monitoring activities to enhance productivity and reduce stress. Among college students, effective time management has been consistently associated with improved academic performance, higher life satisfaction, and better psychological well-being. For instance, Romero et al. (2022) found that mastery-oriented students tend to utilize more structured and effective time management strategies, leading to better academic outcomes.

Conversely, poor time management has been linked to procrastination, decreased academic achievement, and heightened levels of anxiety and stress (Sirois, 2016). These findings highlight the importance of understanding factors that influence students' ability to manage their time effectively. One such factor is personality, particularly the Big Five Personality Traits, which include openness, conscientiousness, extraversion, agreeableness, and neuroticism.

Existing studies suggest that conscientiousness is strongly associated with effective time management behaviors (Douglas et al., 2016). However, findings related to other personality traits remain inconsistent, indicating the need for further empirical investigation. Moreover, while some studies in Southeast Asia, such as those conducted in Indonesia (Susanti et al., 2024) and Davao, Philippines (Arapoc et al., 2024) have explored the relationship between personality and time-related constructs, there remains a scarcity of research focusing specifically on private and university college students in regions such as CALABARZON.

This gap underscores the necessity of examining how personality traits influence time management within the Philippine educational context. Addressing this gap is particularly relevant as higher education institutions

increasingly adopt student-centered learning approaches, requiring students to exercise greater autonomy in managing their time.

This study supports Sustainable Development Goal 4 (Quality Education) by contributing to improved educational outcomes through understanding behavioral and psychological factors that enhance student productivity and academic success.

Research Questions

This study aimed to determine the relationship between time management and Big Five Personality Traits among college students in private institutions.

Specifically, it sought to answer the following questions:

1. What is the level/degree of time management skills of respondents?
2. What is the level of personality traits, in terms of Big Five Personality Traits?
 - 2.1 Conscientiousness
 - 2.2 Extraversion
 - 2.3 Agreeableness
 - 2.4 Neuroticism
 - 2.5 Openness
3. Is there a significant relationship between the time management skills and personality traits?

Scope and Delimitation of the Study

This study focuses on examining the relationship between time management skills and the Big Five personality traits among college students enrolled in private institutions within the Bacoor area during the Academic Year 2026–2027. It specifically measures three dimensions of time management—short-range planning, long-range planning, and time attitudes—and five personality traits: openness, conscientiousness, extraversion, agreeableness, and neuroticism. The study utilizes a quantitative, correlational research design to determine the degree and direction of the relationship between these variables using standardized instruments such as the Time Management Questionnaire (TMQ) and a Big Five Personality scale. The respondents are limited to 100 college students aged 18 years and above who are currently enrolled and voluntarily agreed to participate in the study. The study is delimited to the use of self-report survey questionnaires and focuses only on selected private college students within a specific geographic location, which may limit the generalizability of the findings to other regions or types of institutions. It does not consider other potential factors that may influence time management, such as academic workload, socioeconomic status, motivation, or environmental influences. Additionally, the study does not establish cause-and-effect relationships, as it employs a non-experimental correlational design. The findings are therefore limited to identifying associations between variables rather than determining causal effects

Literature Review

Time Management in Academic Settings

Time management has been widely recognized as a critical factor in academic success. Studies indicate that students who effectively allocate their time tend to achieve higher academic performance and experience lower stress levels. Romero et al. (2022) emphasized that mastery-oriented students demonstrate superior time management skills, suggesting that motivation plays a role in how students organize their tasks. Similarly, Rodaniel (2024) found that students with higher perceived control over time perform better academically and exhibit stronger problem-solving skills. On the other hand, Sirois (2016) highlighted the negative consequences of poor time management, including procrastination and increased psychological distress. These findings underscore the importance of fostering effective time management skills among college students.

Personality Traits and Behavioral Outcomes

The Big Five Personality Traits have been extensively studied in relation to various behavioral outcomes. Conscientiousness has consistently been identified as a strong predictor of organized and goal-directed behavior. Douglas et al. (2016) found that conscientious individuals are more likely to engage in structured time management practices. However, relationships involving other traits such as openness, extraversion, agreeableness, and neuroticism have produced mixed results across studies.

Personality and Time Management

Recent studies have explored the link between personality traits and time-related behaviors. Arapoc et al. (2024) demonstrated a relationship between time perspectives and personality traits among Filipino students, while Susanti et al. (2024) confirmed the association between conscientiousness and time management in an Indonesian context. Despite these findings, there remains limited research focusing on specific educational settings, particularly private colleges in the Philippines. Lipon et al. (2019) further suggested that individual psychological factors, such as personality, should be examined alongside environmental variables to better understand time management behaviors. This highlights the need for integrative studies that consider both internal and external influences.

Methodology

Research Design

The researcher employed a Correlational research design. According to Cherry (2025) A correlational study is a research design that examines the relationship between two or more variables. It is non-experimental, meaning the experimenter does not manipulate or control any variable. In this study, researchers used survey-questionnaires to the respondents since it was made by structured questions to gather all the numerical data, examined the statistical correlation of time management and personality traits. The data collected is based on consistency, validity, and reliability. The research design of the Correlation of the Time Management and Personality Traits among college student aims measure if there is a significant relationship between the variables, which are time management and personality traits.

Sampling Design

The population consisted of college students enrolled in a private institution. A non-probability sampling technique, specifically purposive sampling, was employed due to accessibility and availability of respondents.

Research Locale

The study was conducted in selected private colleges and universities located in the Bacoor area, Cavite, Philippines. These institutions provide a suitable setting for examining the relationship between time management skills and personality traits, as they cater to diverse student populations enrolled in various academic programs from first-year to fourth-year levels. The locale was chosen due to accessibility and the presence of students who are actively engaged in student-centered learning environments, where independent time management is essential. The respondents consisted of currently enrolled college students aged 18 years and above during the Academic Year 2026–2027, ensuring that participants have sufficient academic exposure and experience in managing academic and personal responsibilities within a higher education context.

Research Participants

This study targeted a total of 100 respondents to complete the survey, as quantitative research methodology generally considers a sample size of 100 to 200 participants as an appropriate minimum for descriptive and correlational studies, although it may be insufficient for more complex analyses (Memon et al., 2020). The respondents consisted of college students currently enrolled in various colleges and universities in the Bacoor area during the Academic Year 2026–2027, ranging from first-year to fourth-year levels. To be included in the study, respondents had to be at least 18 years of age or older and must voluntarily agree to participate by signing an informed consent form. Conversely, individuals were excluded from the study if they were not officially enrolled at the college level, were below the age of 18, or declined to provide voluntary consent. This selection criteria ensured that all participants were legally capable of consent and relevant to the objectives of the study.

Research Instrument

This study utilized standardized questionnaires to measure time management and personality traits, with established reliability and validity from previous research. Reliability was ensured through internal consistency measures such as Cronbach's alpha, while validity was supported by prior empirical studies and expert evaluation. Time management was assessed using the Time Management Questionnaire (TMQ) developed by Britton and Tesser (1991), which has an overall Cronbach's alpha of 0.86 and consists of 18 items under three dimensions: short-range planning, time attitudes, and long-range planning. Responses were measured using a five-point Likert scale, with higher scores indicating better time

management practices. Previous studies have shown that effective time management is associated with improved academic performance. Personality traits were measured using the Big Five Personality Trait Model, which includes openness, conscientiousness, extraversion, agreeableness, and neuroticism, and has strong reliability ($\alpha = 0.88$) and good validity. Overall, the instruments used are standardized, unbiased, and appropriate for assessing students' time management behaviors and personality traits.

Data Gathering Procedure

The data gathering procedure is a way to know the process of the study in conducting data to the respondents, to align in the reliability of the assessment. Securing the proposal, all needed documents for the research study, researcher will securely proceed on the next stage. Distribution of letter of consent and letter of intent, in this way the research study will go through a right process for the respondents wherein the consent form will be given to ensure that the respondents are aware of the study and the letter of intent is the approval letter wherein the institution is aware that the research will be having a data gathering to the students of the institution. Next, securing the consent form, the identity or personal information of the respondents will be secure, it is confidential that only the researcher will utilize the respondents' papers. Proceeding to survey questionnaires, this will be utilizing all the data of the respondents, at the same time securing their answers. Summary of the results, then will go through the statisticians, will be the one to interpret the given data of the researcher to test the hypothesis. To draw conclusions and generalization of the populations of the research study.

Results and Discussions

Research Question 1: What is the level/degree of time management skills of respondent?

Table 1. Time Management Skills

	Statements	Mean	SD	Remarks
1.	I make a list of the things that I have to do each day.	3.83	0.37	Always
2.	I make a schedule of the activities that I have to do on work days.	2.83	0.38	Often
3.	I plan the day before I start it.	3.45	0.50	Always
4.	I write a set of goals for myself for each day.	2.91	0.28	Often
5.	I have a clear idea of what I want to accomplish during the next week.	2.92	0.82	Often
6.	I spend time each day planning.	3.27	0.71	Always
7.	I set and honor priorities.	2.92	0.53	Often
8.	I continue unprofitable routines or activities.	3.37	0.55	Always
9.	I believe that there is room for improvement in the way I manage my time.	3.04	0.49	Often
10.	I find myself doing things which interfere with my college work simply because I hate to say "No" to people.	2.77	0.58	Often
11.	I feel I am in charge of my own time, by and large.	3.57	0.58	Always
12.	On an average class day I spend more time with personal grooming than doing college work.	2.98	0.39	Often
13.	I make constructive use of time.	3.82	0.39	Always
14.	The night before a major assignment is due, I am still working on it.	3.09	0.45	Often
15.	I have a set of goals for the entire quarter.	2.71	0.49	Often
16.	I keep my desk clear of everything other than what I am currently working on.	3.65	0.52	Always
	Weighted Mean	3.17	0.14	Often

The results indicate that the respondents generally demonstrate good time management skills, as reflected by the overall weighted mean of 3.17, interpreted as "Often". Many of the specific behaviors associated with effective time management such as making lists of tasks, planning the day before it begins, setting goals, organizing materials, reviewing notes, and making constructive use of time were practiced consistently, with several items rated as "Always". This suggest that most respondents engage regularly in proactive planning and prioritizing behaviors that support academic productivity. However, there are also areas that show room for improvement. Some items, such as avoiding unprofitable activities, managing distractions caused by social obligations, and setting long-term goals, received lower mean scores, indicating these habits are practiced less consistently. Additionally, personal grooming taking precedence over school tasks (Item 12) reflects a potential

misallocation of time for some respondents. Overall, the data suggest that while students exhibit strong foundational time management habits, they could further enhance their effectiveness by reducing time-wasting activities, strengthening goal-setting behaviors, and minimizing distractions. The results were analyzed using the mean, standard deviation, and Pearson's correlation coefficient to interpret the levels of each variable and the relationship between them. Results are presented in tabular form for clarity and are followed by comprehensive discussion, so as the results showed that on table 1 the level/degree of time management skills of respondents, the results indicate that the respondents generally demonstrate good time management skills, as reflected by the overall weighted mean of 3.17, interpreted as "Often". This suggest that most respondents engage regularly in proactive planning and prioritizing behaviors that support academic productivity. However, there are also areas that show room for improvement. Overall, the data suggest that while students exhibit strong foundational time management habits, they could further enhance their effectiveness by reducing time-wasting activities, strengthening goal-setting behaviors, and minimizing distractions.

Research Question 2: What is the level of personality traits, in terms of Big Five Personality Trait?

Table 2. Level of Conscientiousness

Statement	Mean	SD	Remarks
1. I am always prepared	3.26	1.17	Neutral
8. Leave my belongings around.	3.10	1.16	Neutral
13. Pay attention to details	4.30	0.76	Agree
18. Make a mess of things.	2.97	1.47	Neutral
23. Get chores done right away.	3.66	1.29	Slightly Agree
28. Often forget to put things back in their place.	3.19	1.41	Neutral
33. Like order.	3.68	1.26	Slightly Agree
38. Shrink a schedule.	3.52	1.26	Slightly Agree
43. Follow a schedule	3.41	1.33	Neutral
48. Am I exacting in my work.	3.74	1.19	Slightly Agree
Weighted Mean	3.48	0.45	Slightly Agree

The dimension of Conscientiousness yielded a weighted mean of 3.48, interpreted as slightly agree, suggesting that respondents generally possess traits such as organization, responsibility, and diligence. They tend to be attentive to details and like order, as reflected by higher mean scores on statements like "Pay attention to details" (M = 4.30). However, some still show tendencies toward forgetfulness or disorganization, indicated by lower means in items such as "Often forget to put thing back in their poster place" (M = 3.19). This implies that while students demonstrate moderate levels of conscientiousness behavior, developing stronger habits of consistency and self – discipline would further enhance their academic and personal productivity. Several recent studies suggest that conscientiousness may not directly translate into observable time-management behavior unless it is accompanied by active strategy use and self-regulatory practice. For example, Waldeyer et al. (2022) report that "the effect of conscientiousness on academic performance is mediated by using effort regulation strategies and time management strategies," while Trentepohl et al. (2022) observe that "students cannot necessarily transfer their strategy knowledge into strategy use." These findings indicate that conscientiousness may predispose students to be organized in principle, but actual time-management behavior depends on whether they adopt and practice concrete strategies (Bidjerano & Dai, 2007; Fu et al., 2025).

Table 2.1. Level of Extraversion

Statement	Mean	SD	Remarks
1. Am the life of the party.	2.17	1.04	Slightly Disagree
6. Don't talk a lot.	2.93	1.44	Neutral
11. Feel comfortable around people.	2.90	1.08	Neutral
16. Keep in the background.	3.46	1.17	Slightly Agree
21. Start conversations.	3.13	1.52	Neutral
26. Have little to say.	3.31	1.37	Neutral
31. Talk to a lot of different people at parties.	3.68	1.34	Slightly Agree
36. Don't like to draw attention to myself.	3.06	1.44	Neutral
41. Don't mind being the center of attention.	3.25	1.35	Neutral
46. Am quiet around strangers.	3.34	1.31	Neutral
Weighted Mean	3.12	0.38	Neutral

For Extraversion, the weighted mean of 3.12 is interpreted as neutral, implying that respondents neither strongly identify as outgoing nor introverted. The results suggest a balanced social personality where students can adapt to social interactions but may not always seek attention or be the life of the party. Statements such as “Am the life of the party” (M=2.17) scored lower, while “Talk to a lot of different people at parties” (M=3.68) scored higher, reflecting that some students are socially active in selected situations. Overall, the findings indicate that respondents possess moderate social engagement and confidence, showing flexibility in both solitary and group settings.

Table 2.2. Level of Agreeableness

Statement	Mean	Sd	Remarks
2. Feel Little Concern For Others.	3.71	1.14	Slightly Agree
7. Am Interested In People.	3.25	1.52	Neutral
12. Insult People.	1.84	1.26	Slightly Disagree
17. Sympathize With Others' Feelings.	3.80	0.85	Slightly Agree
22. Am Not Interested In Other People's Problems.	3.67	1.36	Slightly Agree
27. Have A Soft Heart.	3.31	1.46	Neutral
32. Am Not Really Interested In Others.	3.61	1.40	Slightly Agree
37. Take Time Out For Others.	3.50	1.35	Slightly Agree
42. Feel Others' Emotions.	3.54	1.33	Slightly Agree
47. Make People Feel At Ease.	3.49	1.41	Slightly Agree
Weighted Mean	3.37	0.45	Neutral

The Agreeableness trait received a weighted mean of 3.37, interpreted as neutral, indicating that respondents tend to be moderately kind, cooperative, and empathetic. They show a fair amount of concern for others and are generally considerate, as supported by higher scores in “Sympathize with others’ feelings” (M=3.80) and “Feel little concern for others” (M=3.71). However, the neutral result suggests that while most respondents strive to be compassionate, there may still be moments of indifference or lack of emotional engagement. This balance reflects realistic interpersonal behavior where students are capable of empathy but may prioritize personal boundaries.

Table 2.3. Level of Neuroticism

Statement	Mean	SD	Remarks
4. Get stressed out easily.	3.32	1.50	Neutral
9. Am relaxed most of the time.	3.40	1.28	Neutral
14. Worry about things.	4.13	1.06	Slightly Agree
19. Seldom feel blue.	3.02	1.20	Neutral
24. Am easily disturbed.	3.57	1.22	Slightly Agree
29. Get upset easily.	3.42	1.34	Slightly Agree
34. Change my mood a lot.	3.32	1.42	Neutral
39. Have frequent mood swings.	3.15	1.53	Neutral
44. Get irritated easily.	3.44	1.27	Slightly Agree
49. Often feel blue.	3.52	1.25	Slightly Agree
Weighted Mean	3.43	0.48	Slightly Agree

The Neuroticism dimension produced a weighted mean of 3.43, which falls under slightly agree. This means respondents tend to experience mild emotional instability, such as stress or worry, but not at an extreme level. Higher scores on statements like “Worry about things” (M=4.13) and “Get irritated easily” (M=3.44) show that students occasionally face emotional fluctuations. However, the neutral ratings on several other items indicate they can generally maintain composure. These results suggest that while some students may be sensitive or anxious at times, they also possess resilience to cope with emotional challenges.

Table 2.4. Level of Openness

Statement	Mean	SD	Remarks
5. Have a rich vocabulary.	3.26	1.27	Neutral
10. Have difficulty understanding abstract ideas.	2.74	1.24	Neutral
15. Have a vivid imagination.	4.15	0.94	Slightly Agree
20. Am not interested in abstract ideas.	3.03	1.40	Neutral
25. Have excellent ideas.	3.43	1.30	Slightly Agree
30. Do not have a good imagination.	3.04	1.46	Neutral
35. Am quick to understand things.	3.29	1.33	Neutral
40. Use difficult words.	3.52	1.33	Slightly Agree
45. Spend time reflecting on things.	3.50	1.44	Slightly Agree
50. Am full of ideas.	3.40	1.34	Neutral
Weighted Mean	3.34	0.45	Neutral

The Openness trait has a weighted mean of 3.34, interpreted as neutral, which means that respondents moderately engage in creativity, curiosity, and intellectual exploration. The statement "Have a vivid imagination" (M=4.15) shows a strong inclination toward creative thinking, whereas lower ratings like "Have difficulty understanding abstract ideas" (M=2.74) suggest some struggle with complex concepts. Overall, this indicates that respondents are open to new ideas and experiences but may vary in how they apply creativity and imagination in academic contexts.

Research Questions 3: Is there a significant relationship between the time management skills and personality traits?

Table 3. Relationship Between Time Management Skills and Personality Traits

Variable	R Value	P Value	Decision	Remarks
Extraversion	0.03026	0.6005	Not Significant	Failed to Reject the Null hypothesis
Agreeableness	0.03057	0.5969	Not Significant	Failed to Reject the Null hypothesis
Conscientiousness	0.03179	0.5825	Not Significant	Failed to Reject the Null hypothesis
Neuroticism	0.00341	0.95301	Not Significant	Failed to Reject the Null hypothesis
Openness	0.16487	0.0034	Significant	Reject the Null Hypothesis

The results show that four of the five personality traits extraversion, agreeableness, conscientiousness, and neuroticism have no significant relationship with the respondents' time management skills. Each of these traits produced p-values greater than the 0.05 significance level, indicating that variations in these personality characteristics do not meaningfully influence how students manage their time. Consequently, the null hypothesis was not rejected for these traits. On the other hand, openness was found to have a significant relationship with time management skills, as shown by its p-value of 0.0034, which is well below the 0.05 threshold. This suggests that students who tend to be curious, imaginative, and open to new experiences are more likely to demonstrate stronger time-management abilities. Because of this significant association, the null hypothesis for openness was rejected. Overall, the findings imply that while most personality traits do not predict time management performance, openness plays a meaningful role in shaping these skills. For the table 3, as the significant relationship between the time management skills and personality traits. The results show that four of the five personality traits extraversion, agreeableness, conscientiousness, and neuroticism have no significant relationship with the respondents' time management skills. Each of these traits produced p-values greater than the 0.05 significance level, indicating that variations in these personality characteristics do not meaningfully influence how students manage their time. Consequently, the null hypothesis was not rejected for these traits. On the other hand, openness was found to have a significant relationship with time management skills, as shown by its p-value of 0.0034, which is well below the 0.05 threshold. Overall, the findings imply that while most personality traits do not predict time management performance, openness plays a meaningful role in shaping these skills.

Ethical Considerations

The researchers will adhere to the provisions of the Data Privacy Act of 2012 to ensure the confidentiality and protection of all respondents. Formal letters were prepared, serving as an informed consent form for the respondents, outlining their voluntary participation. Data will be gathered through survey questionnaires and will be accessible only to the researchers and their research adviser. All information will be utilized strictly for academic purposes, treated with the highest level of care, and safeguarded to prevent any disclosure that may compromise the respondents' privacy or reputation. Collected data will be securely stored and permanently deleted or destroyed after one year. The researchers commit to upholding honesty, integrity, and respect for the respondents throughout the entire research process.

Conclusion

This study aimed to determine the relationship between time management skills and the Big Five personality traits among college students in private institutions. The findings revealed that respondents generally demonstrated good time management skills, as reflected by an overall mean of 3.17, interpreted as "often." This indicates that students regularly practice essential time management behaviors such as planning, organizing, and prioritizing tasks, which support academic productivity. However, the results also highlight areas for improvement, particularly in minimizing time-wasting activities, managing distractions, and strengthening long-term goal setting. In terms of personality traits, the respondents exhibited moderate levels across all dimensions of the Big Five. Conscientiousness showed a slightly higher tendency, suggesting that students possess characteristics such as organization and responsibility, although these traits are not consistently translated into effective time management practices. Extraversion, agreeableness, and openness were generally neutral, indicating balanced social, interpersonal, and cognitive tendencies. Neuroticism was slightly elevated, suggesting that students occasionally experience emotional fluctuations such as stress and worry but still maintain resilience. Furthermore, the results revealed that four personality traits—extraversion, agreeableness, conscientiousness, and neuroticism—had no significant relationship with time management skills. Thus, the null hypothesis was accepted for these variables. However, openness demonstrated a statistically significant relationship with time management, leading to the rejection of the null hypothesis for this trait. This finding suggests that students who are more open to new ideas, creative thinking, and intellectual exploration are more likely to exhibit effective time management behaviors. Overall, the study concludes that while personality traits may influence students' tendencies, time management is not significantly determined by most personality dimensions, except for openness.

Recommendations

Based on the findings of the study, several recommendations are proposed for students, educators, institutions, and future researchers. Students are encouraged to improve their time management by setting clear goals, prioritizing tasks, and reducing distractions. Since openness is linked to better time management, students may also benefit from being flexible, trying new strategies, and adapting to academic demands. Educators are advised to incorporate time management training into their teaching through structured schedules, planning activities, and tasks that promote self-regulation and independent learning. They should also consider individual differences and support both organization and creative problem-solving skills. Institutions are encouraged to offer programs, workshops, and support services such as counseling and mentoring to enhance students' productivity and academic performance. Lastly, future researchers should use larger and more diverse samples and explore other factors such as motivation, workload, stress, and environment. Employing longitudinal or experimental designs is also recommended to better understand the relationship between personality traits and time management.

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